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A Comparison of Rules Engines for Constraint Checking in a Node.js-based Metamodeling Platform

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Abstract

Enterprise modelling is an academic discipline but it is also applied in companies which consists in producing models usable by the organization's actor. These models make it possible to represent the various aspects of the company's interests. The tools used to create these models must integrate the possibility of managing rules relating to the creation of entities, their placement, possible connections, or any other business guideline. This work is a comparison of a subset of rule engines in a web-based meta modelling tool. The test architecture includes an Express.JS server and a Postgresql database. Different tests are conducted on the performance level with response time and rule execution time, but this work also analyses the flexibility of the different solutions. There already exists several papers comparing rule engines. However, the studies focus on a particular aspect, such as performance or the architecture supporting these systems. We have compared five open source solutions that can be integrated directly into a JavaScript environment. These solutions are analysed as a whole and provides decision keys for professionals wishing to determine a solution for their production environment. The results found are similar in terms of performance, but there are large differences in terms of scalability and capacity. The results show a strong optimization of the libraries used and potentially a bottleneck at the Express.js server level, which underlines the importance of a good infrastructure needed to optimize the rules engine.

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1 Introduction

In this chapter we will introduce the research topic and the context related to it. The problems related to the topic will also be formulated. Finally, the different research questions will be derived to place the research in a general context.

1.1 Motivation

In order to identify the importance of modelling, let us derive the famous house building example [Zac87], imagine that we want to build a retail outlet. We will need to construct the building, but also know how to place the rooms, aisles, checkouts, etc. Doing everything without representation is a complicated task for many reasons. The resources are limited, the means available are limited, the time window for the project is fixed, the project requires the collaboration of multiple actors with different skills, etc. It's therefore necessary to make strategic choices in order to carry out the project successfully. Modelling allows these strategic decisions to be made through specific models for certain purposes. For example, architectural plans are used for the construction of the building, flow models for the placement of the shelves to make the shopping experience as smooth as possible, or a model from marketing to determine the placement of products in the shelves. IT projects are similar to the construction of a building, strategic choices have to be made at several levels in order to complete it successfully.

Modelling Modelling allows representations of real systems to be created by subtracting a certain amount of unimportant elements from the model. For example, it is not necessary to represent electric fields in a model designed to optimize the aerodynamics of a car. Indeed, magnetism has a priori little or no impact on the aerodynamics of a vehicle. In order to ensure the consistency of a model, it is necessary to know how to handle the different elements of the model. Different instances of models can be governed by similar rules. Meta modelling describes these common rule sets within a model. This will serve as a basis for designing instances of a certain type of model.

Enterprise Modelling A common definition of enterprise modelling is "a set of activities dealing with representing and describing the structure, behaviour and organisation of whole or part of a business entity" [Ver20, p. 4]. There is no single type of business model, because of the complexity of the business world. Indeed, it's only possible to represent a fraction of it at a time [Ver20]. However, due to its relatively broad definition, modelling is integrated into the daily work of a company and not only by engineers and designers. This practice has some problems as mentioned in other related work [San+18] such as

- The diversification of models is very large, ranging from business processes to organizational role models.
- The wide scope of modelling is hard to catch the whole aspect of the enterprise, and it's even harder when considering cross enterprise model.
- They must not only represent the state as it is at the moment or in the future, but also the steps in the modelling process that led to this state.

From these problems stems an idea that has been popular in model design for a decade: the specificity of models rather than their evolvability. Indeed, it is only recently that the concept of scalability has been put forward in the choice of modelling solutions. It is difficult to foresee with precision how to adapt a model according to future changes [FL16]. This is why, it's important to give the designer the possibility to modify and increase the tools at their disposal. In order to achieve this goal, it's necessary for designers to have a deep understanding of the concepts being modelled in order to make the meta model as generic as possible while remaining specific.

Meta modelling Meta model allows a model to be described by another model. This allows the elements of model instances to be generalized directly. Like model are generalization of the real world, meta models are abstraction of a specific model. Meta models are used to define new model structure or to extends already existing models. Rules can be applied to specific objects of the meta models to enforce or restrict behaviour when creating models. However, it is not possible for developers to create a meta metamodel integrating all possible rules of all model classes. For example, it is possible to integrate a rule to limit the addition or deletion of certain meta classes, or a framework to manage the connection between different meta classes. But some model classes have very specific rules, for example a rule in BPMN: An event gateway must have either a catching intermediate event or Receive task on each gate. This rule requires the presence of another class in a model. It is therefore necessary to give the meta designer the possibility of creating rules on these meta objects himself. In the Adoxx tool [FK13], AdoScript allows to create this kind of rule. A rule engine is therefore perfectly suited for this kind of task. However the choice of which rule engine to choose is the subject of this work. However, are all the proposed products comparable in terms of performance? Research is being conducted to compare the performance of different solutions such as the OpenRuleBench [Lia+09]. The functionality and limitations of the various solutions are at the discretion of the provider.

Performances The results of performance tests in IT are very relevant to a specific time. What was true in 2009 may no longer be true in 2022 due to technological advances and newer, more powerful algorithms. Therefore, it's important to combine performances and features to have the latest knowledge in determining which system is preferable to another. The purpose of this bachelor's work is to understand the most popular solutions on the market and compare their features, limitations, and performance. This contributes to an overview of the current status of the state of the art and provide a decision support in the context of integration into a web-based environment.

The paper begins by identifying a subset of the solutions available on the market, both open source and private then we create a comparison of them. Based on the metamodel presented in Figure 2, implementation examples are developed to show the advantages and limitations of the solution. The evaluation concludes the comparative technical part of the bachelor's work.

This leads to the following research questions:

- Research Question 1: How can we ensure that the data provided by the user is consistent with a meta model?
- Research Question 2: How can current ready-to-use (i.e. non-theoretical) verification tools be integrated into a web environment?
- Research Question 3: How can we compare different rule engine solutions?

1.2 Methodology And Structure

In this sub-chapter, we will describe the research methodology and how the solutions were researched and selected. The context in which these solutions were analysed will be described and clarified to identify the limitations of this analysis. Finally, a critique of the process will be carried out to identify areas for improvement in the analysis.

Search and selection In this phase, the most popular solutions on the market are researched. This ensures consistency between the results and their possible application in the real world. It's necessary to sort out the solutions present on the market to obtain a convincing sample. A too drastic selection would leave out some of the most convincing solutions, while too broad a selection would lead to a waste of time comparing technologies with little or no application to the project.

Implementation The implementation of the selected solutions is a crucial step to test in an environment close to the production environment. This allows us to analyse the ease of implementation but also the various limitations that the creators of the tools may have omitted to mention. It's at this stage that we will test the different approaches to the same problem. Due to the relatively restricted nature of the tests, it's difficult to have a detailed view of the possibilities and limitations of the tools. An emphasis will, however, be put on the adaptability of the solutions in an evolving context with changing needs.

Evaluation The evaluation is a key step, if not the most important step of the work. It's in this phase that we will compare the solutions between them. At the end we will have an overview of what is possible with each solution, but also its limitations. This will lead to a general recommendation on the choice of this type of system. In a constantly changing world, it's important to specify clear search and comparison keys to maximize productivity.

1.2.1 Selection Strategy And Selection Criteria

There exists many types of solutions to extends a meta model [Bac+01; BGP01] and it's impossible to test all of them. This is why it's important to select only those of particular importance in the corporate community or in the open source world.

The main sources of open source projects are of course GitHub ¹ and NPM ². These sites have the advantage of gathering a wide range of opensource projects

¹<https://github.com/>

²<https://www.npmjs.com/>

that can be integrated in the framework of this paper. NPM is a package manager for JavaScripts and TypeScript projects, so it is not necessary to specify a language when searching. Often the projects referenced in NPM link to a GitHub page. In order to find projects in this site, the keywords "Business rule", "rule engine" have been specified to find solutions for this project.

Search Strategy There are two main places to look for tools matching the selection criteria:

- Github: This is a platform run by Microsoft for sharing and managing open source programs. With over 28 million public repositories, it's the largest open-source project sharing library. Anyone can create an account for free and share their project. This is why this site is used by most developers, private and professional, to share their creations. As the site is designed for many different projects, it's important to sort projects in JavaScript or TypeScript only.
- NPM: This is basically a package management tool for JavaScript projects. But the package search tool is powerful and allows you to find tools with their title or description. It's a tool only for JavaScript modules so it isn't necessary to specify a language.

These sites host all kinds of projects, from programs used by millions of people around the world from visual studio code, to student projects made for a course. It's therefore important to sort out the results obtained by the search. Popularity (stars on GitHub and weekly downloads for NPM) is an important indicator to judge the quality of a solution. However, it shouldn't be a criterion to be used isolated, but just a method of eliminating unimportant solutions.

Selection Strategy As specified above, testing all rule engines is impossible. It's therefore important to specify the broadest possible selection criteria while ensuring that the solutions are relevant to the project. Choosing too wide a range of products will lead to results that aren't very applicable to the project. On the other hand, choosing too narrow a range will omit some potentially important solutions. The selection criteria are as follows:

- Open Source: Open source projects are easily accessible and can be maintained by many professionals. The advantage of this paradigm is that the functionality is often close to the needs of the users. Indeed, it's easy to contribute to the improvement of a project to fix a bug or add a feature. Moreover, the algorithms used are visible and can be adapted if the need arises. Closed source projects often work like black boxes. Modifying a feature to best fit the production environment isn't an easy thing to do, if not impossible if one are not the owner of the project.
- Usable In a web environment (i.e. JavaScript or TypeScript): It would be possible to select tools that work as standalone. However such tools add a degree of complexity to the request processing flow. Stand alone projects are often more optimized than libraries. Having to manage these tools separately adds a layer of management and potentially a drop in performance that isn't in the scope of the work.

- Ready-to-use: The selected solutions must be directly integrable in the environment used (i.e. see section Context And Environment). This set aside the theoretical solutions, existing only in scientific literature. Implementing such solutions could lead to better results but the creation of such tool is outside the scope of this project.

These three criteria already greatly reduce the scope of available solutions. The selected tools are considered a state of the art.

1.2.2 Context And Environment

The environment is based on previous work specifying the meta meta-model (noted meta²-model from now) for augmented reality and virtual reality [Muf21; Muf22]. In this work only a part of it is used Figure 2 for the tests but the concepts implemented can be extended to the whole meta²-model.

Figure 1: The basic flow of a request through the server

The environment used in this work is the following:

- Web server: The web server uses the Express.js framework³ for Node.js⁴. This framework is specialized for back-end management for web servers.
- Database: The database system uses Postgresql⁵. Postgresql is one of the most widely used systems in the industry due to its high optimization and flexibility. The database structure used is described in Figure 2. An extract of the actual structure is used in this work for simplicity. Having a description of the complete model is, in our case, not relevant.
- Browser: The browser used for all tests is google Chrome. It's one of the most popular browsers on the market [Sta21]. It's possible to do all the work with another browser such as firefox without major changes.

³see framework here: <https://expressjs.com>

⁴see framework here: <https://nodejs.org/en>

⁵see database system here: <https://www.postgresql.org>

- Testing system: The testing framework is Locust [Jon22] for python. It's a framework that allows the developer to create a load test easily on the server by generating multiple requests simultaneously. It also allows the tester to generate a report summarizing the results obtained.

In the Figure 1, the JSON request containing the model information is transmitted to the HTTP server (in our case with a REST call with the desired operation i.e. POST, PATCH, DELETE). This request must be checked at two levels before it can be accepted by the system.

The first phase is an integrity verification phase. It ensures that the object to be added, modified or deleted meets the integrity constraints of the meta²-model. For example, an instance creation must refer to a meta object already present in the database. This phase isn't the aim of this document, that's why we will consider all the requests as valid up to this stage.

The second test phase is the heart of the matter. Rules are usually applied to a meta object to, for example, restrict the addition of inherited instances of this meta object. These rules are stored in the corresponding table of the database. As we can see on the ER model (see Figure 2), a rule applies only to one meta object. However, such an object can have multiple rules assigned. The method of implementation of the rules is left free depending on the solution used.

In "A methodology and tool support for managing business rules in organizations" [BK05], several types of rules must be present to have a complete environment:

- Rules that triggers a process or an activity. For example, if a user modify a meta model, all the associated model must include the change. Therefor, a message can be forwarded to every user that are currently editing such a model.
- Rules that restricts the executions of a process or an activity. For example the creation or the modification of an object in the model instance can be restricted because the modification does not ensure security.
- Rules that defines an event, conditions or activity structure. Basically every rules can be structured in this way

These rules can be applied in two ways:

- At design time, i.e. at each action performed by the user. This ensures that when the data is saved in the database it conforms to the model. The user can become frustrated by the design process because they have to know how to model before making any changes.
- Periodically, for example when the data is requested to be saved. This option gives the user the freedom to design as they wish and to test the conformity of the model once it's completed.

From an optimization and user comfort point of view, we will assume that the model checks are done on demand. This doesn't matter much because, from a backend technical point of view, an interface (e.g. an endpoint) is called to check the model, and the call can be done after each input of the user or periodically.

1.2.3 Critical Point Of View

This analysis has several points for improvement. Firstly, the selection criteria:

- Open source only: Indeed, limiting oneself to open source projects is practical in terms of accessibility and the ability to analyse internal code. However, it's very restrictive in terms of exploring the solutions available on the market. Indeed, a large part of the solutions are available in the form of licensed software.
- Usable In a web environment only: The solutions available on the market are vast and often specific to a technology or a domain of expertise. This is why many solutions are available as standalone applications. This allows them, at the expense of system adaptability, to be more efficient by directly using the processor and memory of the execution system. Restricting oneself to libraries available for the web written in JavaScript or TypeScript is potentially too limiting to have an overview of the solutions proposed on the market. Moreover, it would be possible to encounter recurrent problems in the libraries that would be linked to the language used. Like security or performance problems [YW09].

As far as the research strategy is concerned, there is little emphasis on projects from the scientific community. This constitutes a large grey area where interesting projects can be discovered. Indeed, some projects have great potential, but don't have the popularity, or the functionality to get the attention of industry. It would be necessary to make a wider selection of the different solutions available on the market to obtain more complete and convincing results.

2 Foundation

In this chapter we will look at how the development landscape has evolved over the last few decades to what it is today. It's a dynamic and complex process that is difficult to capture in its entirety, so we will focus on the evolution of the development paradigm then on the expansion of the web in the technological landscape.

2.1 Modelling

A model in the computer sense is a representation of real events, behaviour or systems present in real life. A model has a higher or lower degree of abstraction depending on the degree of realism desired. Indeed, a very accurate model will be closer to the real world, whereas a model with a high degree of abstraction will not represent reality as accurately. Modelling can be used, for example, for testing [Man+15], prediction [PW98] or visualisation purposes [Ega+97]. There is no specific purpose when it comes to modelling, each user may have its own specific needs. Nevertheless, model building can be summarised in a few basic building blocks:

- Elements that represented real objects, as for example in an architectural drawing software a solid grey rectangle represents a wall of the house.

- Relationships to link the elements together. These links can be real like a copper cable in the real world or not, like a usage of an object A by an entity B.
- Connection rules between objects to restrict the links between elements to obtain a consistent and correct model.

It is possible to perform calculations on these models in order to determine, for example, the aerodynamics of an aircraft or the stability of a steel structure subjected to severe weather conditions.

2.2 Meta Modelling

Meta modelling can be defined in many different ways but according to Hans-Georg Fill and Dimitris Karagiannis[FK13], a meta model is a representation of the abstract syntax of a modelling language but also a model with a concrete representation of its syntax. A meta model uses a modelling language which is described as a meta modelling language. The syntax of the meta modelling language can therefore be represented by a meta meta model. In our case the definition of the modelling language via a meta model implies a fixed meta meta model. In other words, the meta meta model defines all the allowed possibilities of the meta model. It then becomes possible to generalise a model into an instance and thus increase the reusability of the objects in the instance. For example, in a supermarket configuration modelling application, a shelf will be interpreted differently by each department in the shop. For the finance department, a shelf represents income, for the fitters, a shelf is a compartment containing other products, while for the shop builder the shelf is a product in itself. The same meta object can have several different functions in different model instances. There are several meta modelling languages such as UML [RJB04] or the knowledge representation family, Web ontology language 2.0 [Hit+12] or SysML [Hau+06]. Meta languages are generally based on OMG standards [Obj16].

2.3 Constraints

As we have seen in modelling and in meta modelling, it is important to specify constraints on models in order to limit the actions of programmers or users. This can be, for example, limiting the number of specific objects in a model instance (e.g. the "start" object in BPMN can only be present once per the model instance), or the opposite by forcing a minimum number of objects. The UML does not have a mechanism for making such conditions directly, whereas SysML has a "constraint" block for this purpose. It is possible to create a fully hand-crafted constraint system as the adoScript language in the ADOxx (meta) modelling tool [FK13]. Another option is to integrate rule engine systems like in this paper.

3 Related Work

State of the research The first step is to have an overview of the state of research about rules engines and more generally of modelling applied to the web. This step is critical to specify the framework of the project.

3.1 Meta Modelling

There are many different meta modelling systems, each with its own advantages and disadvantages, such as, e.g., Eclipse EMF [Ste+08], Visual Studio DSL Tools [Coo+07], MetaEdit+ [KLR96], ADOxx [FK13], WebGME [Mar+14], and AtomPM [Syr+13]. Meta modelling is a subject that has received more and more attention from researchers with the expansion of new development methods such as model-driven engineering [Sch06].

In metaedit+ rule can be either of any kind of

- Object connectivity in the binding (e.g. an object may be in a certain role at most a specified number of times).
- Object occurrence (e.g. an object type may have only a specified number of instances in a graph).
- Ports involved in binding (e.g. all ports of a specified type in a binding must have the same value for a specified property).
- Property uniqueness (e.g. all objects of a certain type in a graph must have unique values for a specified property).

There is no possibility to create other custom rules that are outside of these types. This is a major drawback in the flexibility because one can imagine a custom metamodel that contains a rule that does not fit in the previous categories. For example, a composition of simple rules linked with IF-ELSE conditions.

In Adoxx the rule creation is done through the AdoScript which gives the much more freedom in terms of adaptability. It has many features to manipulate all the objects present in the meta model and in the instance model. This is a perfect option to extend the possibilities of rule creations, but it has the disadvantage to be a custom language. The community and the support could be limited because the usage of the said script language is bound to the Adoxx tool. Moreover the language being proprietary it might be hard to learn and slower to use than a proper programming language.

In Visual Studio DSL Tools, the rules are written in C# which offer all the features needed to create complex rules. The lack of browser interface (i.e. the tool requires the installation to visual studio) leads to the limitation of usage between various devices (e.g. on android or IOS).

In Eclipse EMF there exists a whole framework to validate a model or a meta model written in Java⁶. As said previously a "proper" developing language is powerful enough to create a complex rules and validation strategies. The use of this type of language limits the accessibility of rule creation to developers only. Moreover, the fact that the framework is separate from the main project can make it tedious to integrate.

In webGME there are two kind of constraint that can be applied to a meta model object's:

- Meta rules: They are designed to limit the inclusion of one object in an other one. For example one can limit the amount of Attributes of a Class to 2.

⁶See Eclipse modelling Validation: <https://www.eclipse.org/modelling/emf/downloads/?project=validation>

- Constraints: These are custom made rule for each meta objects but they are programmed in Javascript. Just like the other two previous solutions this is suboptimal in term of security and accessibility to non-programmer designer.

In AtomPM the rules can be either local (i.e. the rule only "sees" the related object and connected objets) or global (i.e. "sees" the whole model). These constraints are written in JavaScript too and must evaluates to a boolean value. This limit the ability to adapt the model accordingly to the rules. One could for example automatically delete the classes that bloc the model from being accepted (e.g. only one occurrence of a specific class). This scenario is not possible in AtomPM.

The last two solutions are the most similar to the context and environment used in this work. The rule applications strategies are simple but effective and cover most of the use cases. One might have to investigate deeper to see if one can improve these applications.

3.2 Rule Engines

There exists some comparative studies of different rule engines present on the market. In its report [Lia+09], OpenRuleBench, compares several rule engines from different worlds: Prolog-Based Systems, Deductive Databases Systems, Rule Engines for Triples, Production and Reactive Rule Systems, Knowledge-Base System. These tests are conducted from the point of view of the speed of execution of different operations such as large joins and recursions. All of them being of very good engine and optimized since years to reach high performances. But this study doesn't focus on the integration aspect of the different solutions. Indeed, a perfectly optimized solution that can't be integrated into a production environment will be little used. This is why it's important to consider the different compatibility aspects of rule engines before testing for performance.

In "A Business Rule Engine Applied to Egovernment Services Integration" [KM06], the focus is on the integration of rule systems in an Egovernment context. This study is very close to the context of this work by considering the web framework. This paper is oriented towards a more global approach to the integration of rule engines. Indeed, it specifies some use cases, then specifies the optimal architecture to integrate a rule engine solution. This architecture must allow interaction between the different modules making up the system.

In "A Comparison of Mobile Rule Engines for Reasoning on Semantic Web-Based Health Data" [Woe+14] the authors compare different rule engines (AndroJena, RDFQuery, RDFStore-JS and Nools) in a web context and more precisely for mobile devices. The work uses the following comparison keys:

- Time to load rules and data: This is the time needed for pre-processing.
- Computation Time: This is the time needed by the rule engine to evaluate the rules.
- Memory Load: This is the number of kilobytes of RAM used during the execution of the engine.

This study has a very similar methodology to this work but the data acquisition and processing time is considered for the evaluation. The integration part isn't

mentioned, so it may be that the solutions tested are interesting in the context of the study but not in a production environment.

Our Contribution The rule engine for web approach has the advantage to be accessible from any web browser. The language used to specify rules is either a JSON file, a universally known programming language or a standardized language (e.g. OCL). This work aims to compare the different rule engines in a web context. The comparison will not only be made from the point of view of performance but also of usability and scalability. Recent research hasn't combined the two aspects and is either very complete in terms of performance comparison [Lia+09] [Woe+14], or they remain general by defining only the architecture necessary for the implementation of rule engine. This work is placed at the interface of the two approaches. The research and selection method are close to a research that could be carried out by a developer wanting to implement a rule engine solution in a production environment. The general approach of the work is based on a practical aspect to ensure a good transferability of the results in a production environment.

4 Analysis Of The Properties Of The Available Solutions

In this section we will analyse the different solutions found by applying our search and selection method as specified in the chapter 1.2. A brief feature analysis of the different solutions will be performed before implementation.

4.1 Selected Rule Engines

4.1.1 Rools

Rools [The21] is a rule engine which has the advantage of being optimized using the RETE algorithm. RETE is a strong pattern matching algorithm for implementing production rule systems [LGX10]. It also has a conflict resolution mechanism if many rules are to be executed. This option authorizes more flexibility than just applying the rules in order of registration. The tool allow to specify, in addition to the insertion order, a priority index, a refraction boolean (if true each rule is fired at most once) and a specificity index (more specific rules are checked first). In web applications it's common to use asynchronous functions with promises as return type. This library supports these types of functions in both ways of programming, with the "async" "await" keywords or with the "then" keywords. The rule extension mechanism allows to create basic rules that will be extended. This could allow the users to design rule that are more specific by extending a parent rule. Rools automatically optimizes the rules with the same permissions, this allows a rule creation without having to know the whole framework to avoid duplication. This reduce the load on the server and potentially increase the speed of execution by the engine. This gives the user the possibility to create new rule without thinking about how all the other are already implemented. The system will aggregate similar rule together automatically.

4.1.2 Node-rules

Node-rules [Sat21] is a rule-engine that takes rules in JSON format with JavaScript functions as condition and consequences. This is useful to provide a simplified interface for rule creation. The rules of this library can be executed, server side or browser side. This allows a first optimization of the requests. Indeed, the browser can perform a first check before sending the data to the server. This would lead to local warning, finally loading less the server in the design phase. A priority index is present to bypass the insert order execution. The disadvantage of this library although it's light is its lack of options which makes it not very scalable to cover all the problems related to the implementation of the rules.

4.1.3 Json-rules-engine

Json-rules-engine [Ham19] is a rule engine working through JSON files. This tool gives the user the possibility to create multiple rules on the same JSON file. This can be an advantage to chain rule but a drawback when managing such rules. The JSON format makes integration into a web project easier and doesn't require an interface. Indeed, JavaScript and more precisely Node JS are working closely with this format and provide methods, such as `JSON.stringify` or `JSON.parse`. This library is also capable of running on Node JS servers but also on a browser, which increases adaptability for the same reasons as stated in sub-section 4.1.2. For example, it's possible to execute a pre-test on the client to limit the load on the server. It supports the boolean operators ALL and ANY as well, making the engine more versatile. This gives the option to aggregate rules and creating very complex rules. The feature to do reference to pre-existing rules when designing give the possibility to create a network of rules. This might affect the performances in term of execution speed.

4.1.4 Trools

Trool [max22] is a rule-engine allowing to design rules with a spreadsheet created with an associated tool (e.g. MS excel or Libreoffice calc). Spreadsheets are still widely used in the business world. It's therefore an excellent tool to allow non-technical users to implement and maintain their business rules with minimal efforts. The spreadsheet must be exported in CSV format before it can be processed by the rule-engine. The spreadsheets can therefore be dynamically generated to best fit the context in which the rule is applied. For example by the server that send a download link to the spreadsheet containing all the rules associated to a meta object. The user would modify it and then upload it back on the server to implement the rules.

4.2 Available Other Solutions

In this section one explore tools that were not found in the search phase. These tools could not be automatically integrable in the project. They contains general good ideas that can be used to orientate the work.

4.2.1 OCL

The object constrain language is a complement to the UML. It's now widely used in model-driven engineering, for example in code generation for activity models [SS18]. It's important to give users the possibility to extend a model by additional constraints. As we can see in Figure 2, some objects can require conditions to their creation (maximum number in a scene) or to their deletion (mandatory link between a class and another). OCL is based on the principle of expression evaluation. They can be

- Invariant: The expression needs to check all conditions to be satisfied
- Instantiative of class properties: The expression is used to instantiate the property of a specific class.
- Derivation rules: These describe how values derived from the model should be computed
- Query operations: These require information from the system to return it to the user.
- Operations contracts: i.e. a set of pre and post conditions

OCL is a typed language, which means that each expression evaluates to a type (either a user-defined type or a predefined type). The language prevents direct modification of models, it's side effect free. With this specification, it will be necessary to implement an external solution to modify the user's inputs before storing them in the server.

This language offers many possibilities but requires an interface to be integrated in a Node JS web environment. There exists a tools named OCL.js [Kön18] that parse the OCL code into a JavaScript understandable language. The library offers the advantage that the designer of the rules must not learn a new grammar to start implementing them. However, not all the OCL functions are implemented by OCL.js.

4.2.2 Eclipse GLSP

Eclipse graphical language server platform is an open-source framework allowing the creation of diagrams based on a meta model. GLSP client works through a web browser that is used to design models. There exists some differences between this tool and the test environment used in this paper. The first is that the communication between the backend and the frontend is done with a protocol specific to the Eclipse framework, the graphical language server protocol. Specifying a custom communication protocol have a huge advantage beside taking a certain amount of time to create: the flexibility. Using only endpoints can lead to slow reaction time because the HTTP protocol is not optimised specifically for this purpose. The GLSP tool gives the possibility to create their own backend server in Node JS⁷. The general idea is great and many lessons could be learned from this implementations.

⁷<https://github.com/eclipse-glsp/glsp-server-node>

4.3 Example Used

Business rules engines are environments for executing business rules. The rules can be classified in four categories according to the business rule group [Grone]:

1. Definition of a business term: This is the most basic rule, it translates the term used in the real world as understandable expressions for the engine.
2. Facts relating terms to each other: Here the terms are related to each other. For example, a customer can have a discount of 10% if they are a gold member.
3. Constrains: Here the rule can accept or reject a modification, for example. A client can place an order if they have more than 10 articles in their basket.
4. Derivations: Here the business rule is the derivation of another one. The knowledge comes from another knowledge in the business.

As mentioned before, it is important to compare the solutions with a set of illustrations covering as much as possible the real use cases. This is why we will consider the following examples:

1. Two trivial rules, one invariably returning a positive answer and the other always returning a negative answer. These two instances are intended to test the rapidity of execution with rules of a minimal complexity of $O(1)$, this will also allow to chain trivial rules to test the speed of execution with a complexity of $O(n)$ for n rules.
2. A rule allowing to limit a class instance to a single occurrence. This example is applicable in cases such as in BPMN models which cannot have more than one start or end class.
3. Rule counting the number of occurrences of an object, in our case a specific class in the whole model. This is done in the way of a complement of rule 2 (more than one occurrence of a specific class). Indeed we need to be able to count occurrences of a specific class to check if it occurs more than once.

These examples will be implemented in the same web server but will be isolated by different endpoints. This will allow to challenge simultaneously the different solutions on a strictly equal test data set. The different executions being hermetic between them it will not impact the performances. Moreover the tests will be done in a sequential way and not concurrently to avoid influencing one test by another.

4.4 Key Comparison Points

In the current systems there exists several types of tests for a web server [ZFL10]:

1. The stress test and load test: Are carried out by gradually increasing the load on the system to determine at which point the performances become unacceptable. The load can be increased by simulating simultaneous users. An important indicator is the average response time as a function of the number of users.

-
2. **Streight Tests:** These are stress/load tests but spaced several hours or even days apart. They discover errors that are often difficult to detect, such as memory leaks, or blocking processes that do not leave the critical zone.

There exists particular measures to determine the optimization of a web server specifically:

1. **The response time:** It is the period between the instant when the user sends a request to the server and the moment when they receive a complete correct answer. The return of an HTTP error (e.g. 500 internal server error) is not considered because it is counted as a failed request.
2. **Throughput:** This is the number of requests the server can serve in a time window. The most commonly used unit is requests/seconds. It is a measure that often goes hand in hand with response time.
3. **Resource Usage:** This gauge collects data on CPU load, memory, network usage, and potential other hardware factors. They are intended to determine a bottleneck from a hardware perspective.

In our case we will perform a load test using the Locust tool [Jon22] by progressively increasing the number of virtual users from 0 to 400 on the same endpoint. The indicators we will collect are the minimum, maximum and average response time for successfully answered requests, but also the number of failed requests (in percent of the number of requests). The use of hardware is not tested because the tests do not aim at highlighting a performance improvement depending on the hardware but on the type of rule used. The flexibility of the different solutions will also be discussed. Indeed a solution could be optimized in terms of response time but inflexible which would make it not unpractical in a dynamic environment.

5 Implementation And Examples

The integration of libraries is fast and easy with the npm package manager⁸. The implementation of the rules for the different languages is available in the Table 1.

⁸<https://www.npmjs.com/>

Figure 2: The ER model used in the server

	Trivial rule true	Trivial rule false	One start rule	More than one start rule
OCL	<pre> context SomeInstance in obviouslyTrueOCLRule: 2=2 </pre>	<pre> context SomeInstance in obviouslyFalseOCLRule: 1=2 </pre>	<pre> context SomeInstance in oneStartEvent: self.class_instances->asSet()-> collect(classInst: ClassInstance -- classInst.uid.class == "d400024b-1d52-473f-a104-3b131c3867e")-> size() <= 1 </pre>	<pre> context SomeInstance in MoreThanOneStart: self.class_instances->asSet()-> collect(classInst: ClassInstance -- classInst.uid.class == "d400024b-1d52-473f-a104-3b131c3867e")-> size() >= 1 </pre>
JSON rule engine	<pre> { "conditions": { "and": { "fact": "boolean", "operator": "equal", "value": true } }, "event": { "type": "obviouslyTrueRule", "params": { "message": "The true rule has been triggered" } } } </pre>	<pre> { "conditions": { "and": { "fact": "boolean", "operator": "equal", "value": false } }, "event": { "type": "obviouslyFalseRule", "params": { "message": "The false rule has been triggered" } } } </pre>	<pre> { "conditions": { "and": { "fact": "class_instances", "path": "\${?}/@.uid.class == \"d400024b-1d52-473f-a104-3b131c3867e\"", "operator": "countLessThan", "value": 2 } }, "event": { "type": "one_start_event", "params": { "message": "More than one start is present" } } } </pre>	<pre> { "conditions": { "and": { "fact": "class_instances", "path": "\${?}/@.uid.class == \"d400024b-1d52-473f-a104-3b131c3867e\"", "operator": "countGreaterThanInclusive", "value": 2 } }, "event": { "type": "more_than_one_start_event", "params": { "message": "Less than two start are present" } } } </pre>
Roos	<pre> { name: 'obviously true rule', when: (facts) => true, then: (facts) => { facts.result.push('Always true rule') } } </pre>	<pre> { name: 'obviously false rule', when: (facts) => false, then: (facts) => { facts.result.push('Always false rule') } } </pre>	<pre> name: 'Only one start class', when: (facts) => { let seen = 0; for (const current_class of facts.object.class_instances) { if (current_class.uid.class === "d400024b-1d52-473f-a104-3b131c3867e") { seen += 1 } } return seen >= 2; }, from: (facts) => { facts.result.push('More than one start event') } } </pre>	<pre> name: 'Only one start class', when: (facts) => { let seen = 0; for (const current_class of facts.object.class_instances) { if (current_class.uid.class === "d400024b-1d52-473f-a104-3b131c3867e") { seen += 1 } } return seen < 2; }, from: (facts) => { facts.result.push('Only one start event') } } </pre>

Table 1: The different implementations of the rule on the server

5.1 OCL.js

The integration of the library is relatively direct and easy. It is, however, necessary to define custom types so that the user can refer to them in the OCL rules (line 11-15 in Appendix B.1). The addition of the rules in the engine is direct and without need of parser since the library parse a string containing OCL code. Providing only a string is necessary. The creation of rules is facilitated by the large documentation available on the net. For example the "OCL: Syntax, Semantics, and Tools" [RG02] describe in detail how to create OCL rules in an optimal way.

5.2 Json-rules-engine

The usage of the Json-rules-engine is fast thanks to its ability to handle JSON objects. As shown in the function implemented in the server (see Appendix B.2), only a few lines are needed to create and execute the engine. It isn't necessary to parse the object to test. Indeed, the engine can take as parameters an object of type Object (in the JavaScript sense of the term). The rules being stored in text format in the database for security reasons must be parsed in JSON, but no external library is necessary. A simple `JSON.parse`⁹ is enough. Successful and failed events can have properties defined by the user or predefined by the developer, like "message" in our example.

5.3 Rools

The implementation of Rools is also relatively fast and direct. However the rules aren't in pure JSON. Indeed there is a JavaScript part inside the JSON rule file. It's impossible to store them in the database then import them dynamically into the engine. Indeed, the rules are made of a "when" part and a "then" part, these two parts take as value an arrow function with as parameter "facts". It's possible to design dynamically these functions thanks to the call to the eval function of JavaScript, but it's highly unadvised for security reasons [YW09]. There exist other solutions to create dynamically these functions but it's still dangerous to execute functions developed by the user directly in the server. In the example the rules aren't imported from the database but hard-coded into the parent function (line 14-53 in Appendix B.3). It's also important to note that it's only possible to return a result if it has been written by a rule. It's impossible, for instance, to always return the name of the rule and its final state (accepted or refused) to notify the user of correctly tested rules.

5.4 Trools

The integration of this tool didn't give conclusive results. Indeed, it was impossible to run the tool even with the code of the example project. However, it's interesting to note that the library converts the CSV file containing the rules into JSON in the background and runs it in its own engine. It would be possible to use the parser to employ the engine of another rule engine but it would take a lot of time and wouldn't bring a notable added value.

⁹more on this function: https://developer.mozilla.org/en-US/docs/Web/JavaScript/Reference/Global_Objects/JSON/parse

6 Evaluation Of The Solutions

Endpoint - Rule	# Requests	# Fails	Average (ms)	Min (ms)	Max (ms)	% fails
Accepting state - OCL	13868	488	1040	3	3938	3.51
Rejecting state - OCL	13713	527	1084	7	4185	3.84
Accepting state - JSON-rules-engine	13906	449	1035	3	3795	3.22
Rejecting state - JSON-rules-engine	13843	489	1088	9	4081	3.53
Accepting state - Rools	13671	473	1047	3	3775	3.45
Rejecting state - Rools	13801	493	1082	7	4191	3.57

Table 2: The performances for each rule engine.

6.1 OCL.js

The process of evaluating the rules is as follows:

1. The engine converts the OCL rules (a string containing the OCL code) to a JS format.
2. The engine evaluates the rules one by one against the object specified by the user and returns true if the rule isn't fired and false otherwise.

6.1.1 Advantages

OCL.js have for principal advantage to be based on the OCL language which is an international standard¹⁰. There exists thus a community using the language for various projects of modelling. Moreover this language is turing-complete, which means that it's theoretically possible to computerize any rule [CK04]. The tested object (fact) doesn't need to be processed before being passed as a parameter to the engine. Moreover the structure of the object is accessible in the rule as long as the structure has been registered beforehand (see Appendix B.1).

6.1.2 Disadvantages

The OCL.js library is maintained by a single person (Stephan Königer) and hasn't been updated for nearly 4 years. It's thus relatively frozen and will probably not have any update to come. All OCL functions aren't implemented in the library¹¹. It would be necessary to implement internally the missing functions. It's impossible to return values other than true or false and the name given inside the rule. Because of this constraint, it's impossible, for example, to modify an object before passing it to the next middleware, or to return a message. The library being composed of two main parts, a parser and an interpreter, it would be possible to integrate these scenarios internally.

6.2 Json-rules-engine

6.2.1 Advantages

The Json-rules-engine has the huge advantage of handling only JSON objects which is native in JavaScript. The rules are of the form in Listing 1 The various requests on the endpoints, whether POST or PATCH, are made in JSON format.

¹⁰see <https://www.omg.org/spec/OCL/> for the specification

¹¹list of implemented feature: <https://ocl.stekoe.de/#implemented-language-features>

```

{
  conditions: {
    all: [
      {
        fact: 'fact-name',
        operator: 'equal',
        value: 'value-to-test-against',
        path: '$.property'
      }
    ]
  },
  event: {
    type: 'event-name',
    params: {
      property_x: value
    }
  }
}

```

Listing 1: The template of a JSON rule on Json-rule-engine

This greatly simplifies the management of rule validation. The rules don't need to be parsed with an external tool. It's also possible to implement an interface to help rule creation like the associated project: Rule Editor¹². There exists the option to compose different rules with the operator "any" or "all" which allows a great flexibility for the user to create complex rules. The provided object (fact) doesn't need to be processed before being passed as a parameter to the engine. The sub-objects of the fact are also accessible in the rule without the need to specify its structure. The access to the different properties is done with jsonpath-plus¹³ which is a port of Xpath for JSON objects. It's thus possible to sort precisely the sub-objects to be tested. It's also possible to create new and more complex operators as needed, as in the implementation (see line 11-16 in Appendix B.2). This allows the user to create more complex tests. One of the great advantages of this library is that the rules are not tested serially by order of registration in the database but can have a priority index which allows to prioritize the rules. The return type of the rules isn't fixed and can be dynamically depending on the context (this is the "message" parameter in Table 1). We can, for example, return a property to be modified with an error message.

6.2.2 Disadvantages

The definition of the rules isn't standardized, it's thus more difficult to find documentation beyond the documentation available on the GitHub of the project[Ham19]. The project hasn't been updated for three years, so it's unlikely that a new version will be released. However the project being open source it's possible to implement new features internally.

¹²<https://www.json-rule-editor.com/#/home>

¹³<https://github.com/json-path/JsonPath>

6.3 Rools

It's impossible to process dynamically and securely the rules that a user would have developed as specified in the implementation part [YW09]. The choice of this solution is therefore in contexts where the rules can be designed by the developer themselves.

6.3.1 Advantages

The rules being objects made up of anonymous JS functions (see line 44 to 52 in Appendix B.3), it's thus possible to create complex rules. One can create external helper methods that would execute, even reuse some already implemented functions elsewhere in the code. The conflict resolution feature gives the option to manage easily the rules. Indeed, the order of applications of the rules can greatly reduce the time needed to proceed. This is not applicable in this context because all the rule must be executed at least once to inform the user of what is wrong in their implementation.

6.3.2 Disadvantage

As specified above, the rules are written in JavaScript. This greatly interferes with the purpose of integrating a rule engine in a web application. Indeed, the rule engine must give the user the possibility to create rules without coding JavaScript functions themselves. Without any simpler interface, it would be easier to simply implement a full JavaScript rule engine that only the developer can extend. Implementing such an interface is a long and tedious task and is outside the scope of this paper.

6.4 Trools

The tool not working in this project, and thus not having been able to be tested. It wasn't considered necessary to comment on its advantages and disadvantages.

6.5 Usability Analysis

There exists big differences in syntax to perform the same action as shown in Table 1. OCL is more concise than other engines both in terms of rule creation and usage. But OCL rules must be stored as text in the database to be translated in code into a rule understandable by the OCL.js engine. This storage as text prevents optimizing the upstream processing of the rules, for example by checking their integrity. JSON rules are longer than those of other engines but are usually more explicit and allow more possibilities, such as the composition of several rules with OR and AND. The priority index is a great option to reorganize the application order of the rules. The ability to specify custom return types is a huge advantage in terms of flexibility. We could imagine using the rule to suggest the changes that must be made to the model to comply to the rules. Since the rules are written in JSON, one can save them directly in the same format in a database and thus optimize their processing more easily. Indeed, there exists options to query directly the content of the JSON stored value through SQL queries. Near every relation database system offer a degree of optimization when sorting JSON content [Pet17]. It's possible to check the

integrity of the rules relatively easily before storing them in the database. Rools rules are as explicit as JavaScript can be, with arrow functions as the logic engine.

6.6 Performances Analysis

All the rules engines tested offer the same performance in terms of response speed and error rate (see Appendix 7). This can be explained in several ways:

1. There is a bottle neck elsewhere in the server, either upstream by processing the request, or downstream by processing and returning the response.
2. The rules aren't large enough in terms of complexity to show significant differences. This can occur when the increase in rule processing time isn't linear or polynomial but exponential.
3. The underlying evaluation methods of the rule engines are essentially the same (i.e. parsing the rules and the object to be tested in JavaScript). Then the object is passed in the parameter of the rules transcribed in JavaScript functions. This only leads to minor changes in performance.

The error rate for all rule engines is below 4%, which is a good performance considering the maximum load of 400 simultaneous users and more than 30 requests per second per endpoint.

However, OCL.js generates the highest number of errors at high server loads. This is still acceptable with 3.51% time-out for requests accepting an object and 3.84% for requests rejecting an object. Rools doesn't have a higher performance than the other two engines although the rules aren't parsed before being added into the rule engine. Json rule engine is the last in terms of speed of processing of blocking rules with 9 ms, which could announce longer execution times than the other two engines in case of more complex rules.

7 Discussion And Conclusion

In this section we will interpret the results obtained in the section 6. We will then put these results into perspective with other studies on the same subject or evaluating the same solutions. The limitations of these results will also be discussed to have a critical look at them. The conclusion will take the form of a general summary of the work with a general vision of it.

Discussion In this context, there exists no fundamental difference in performance between the different engines tested (see Table 2). This may be because they rely on the same processing dynamics (described in section 6.6). However, grammar of the rules has important differences. It's possible to select a standardized syntax for projects involving actors specialized in modelling and knowing specific languages like OCL. But it's also possible to choose a rule engine with a custom syntax such as JSON rules engine. It can be more easily adapted to the context and the skill level of the rule creators. A third option is to create rules in pure JavaScript for optimal performance and flexibility at the expense of readability. Indeed, only developers will be able to maintain these rules. Although the Trools engine doesn't work, its concept is still interesting:

having a rules management interface with a spreadsheet is an excellent idea. Indeed, a large majority of companies use such software, which would make the creation and maintenance of rules easier for users while reducing the resistance to change due to the introduction of such a solution. A fixed model could be created with a simplified interface (i.e. form control in excel¹⁴). It would export the data in a server-translatable format like CSV, for example. Other solutions are available on the market, all offering their advantages and disadvantages. This work has deliberately focused on open-source and web-oriented rule engines, it has also been selected to bring a great importance to the ease of use by the users.

The results of other research are variable. For example, the work "A Comparison of Mobile Rule Engines for Reasoning on Semantic Web-Based Health Data" [Woe+14] is a comparison of rule engines in the context of health data in a semantic web environment. In the conclusion of this study, the differences between the mobile rule engines are hardly noticeable in small data processing. However, when processing large amounts of data, there is a large difference in performance in terms of response time. In their report on OpenRuleBench [Lia+09], they found similar results when the size of the data to be processed is increased. The results of these two studies show an increase in processing time when the number of data to be processed is increased. In our work the number of data to process is increased with the number of users querying the different engines.

Conclusion In the world of web development, there exists not, generally, a perfect product when selecting a solution. In this paper, we have highlighted the different reasons for such a choice. Performance should be, kept in mind, but the user experience should remain a priority. A fast but not very ergonomic product will be unpopular. The flexibility of the solutions must also have a special place in the deliberations. Without wanting a solution that will handle all future problems and use cases, one must choose a solution that is flexible and can adapt to the context.

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¹⁴more details: <https://support.microsoft.com/en-us/office/overview-of-forms-form-controls-and-activex-controls-on-a-worksheet-15ba7e28-8d7f-42ab-9470-ffb9ab94e7c2?ocmsassetid=ha010237663&correlationid=d940ea03-db21-4b12-a0f5-5add189939b5&ui=en-us&rs=en-us&ad=us>

Bibliography

- [Zac87] John A Zachman. “A framework for information systems architecture”. In: *IBM systems journal* 26.3 (1987), pp. 276–292.
- [KLR96] Steven Kelly, Kalle Lyytinen, and Matti Rossi. “Metaedit+ a fully configurable multi-user and multi-tool case and came environment”. In: *International Conference on Advanced Information Systems Engineering*. Springer, 1996, pp. 1–21.
- [Ega+97] SS Egan et al. “Three-dimensional modelling and visualisation in structural geology: new techniques for the restoration and balancing of volumes”. In: *Proceedings of the 1996 Geoscience Information Group Conference on Geological Visualisation. Electronic Geology Special Volume*. Vol. 1. 1997, pp. 67–82.
- [PW98] Edzer J Pebesma and Cees G Wesseling. “Gstat: a program for geostatistical modelling, prediction and simulation”. In: *Computers & Geosciences* 24.1 (1998), pp. 17–31.
- [Bac+01] Kenneth Baclawski et al. “Extending UML to Support Ontology Engineering for the Semantic Web”. In: *UML 2001 — The Unified Modeling Language. Modeling Languages, Concepts, and Tools*. Ed. by Martin Gogolla and Cris Kobryn. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2001, pp. 342–360. ISBN: 978-3-540-45441-0.
- [BGP01] L. Baresi, F. Garzotto, and P. Paolini. “Extending UML for modeling Web applications”. In: *Proceedings of the 34th Annual Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences*. 2001, 10 pp.-. DOI: 10.1109/HICSS.2001.926350.
- [RG02] Mark Richters and Martin Gogolla. “OCL: Syntax, Semantics, and Tools”. In: *Object Modeling with the OCL: The Rationale behind the Object Constraint Language*. Ed. by Tony Clark and Jos Warmer. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2002, pp. 42–68. ISBN: 978-3-540-45669-8. DOI: 10.1007/3-540-45669-4_4. URL: https://doi.org/10.1007/3-540-45669-4_4.
- [CK04] María Victoria Cengarle and Alexander Knapp. “OCL 1.4/5 vs. 2.0 Expressions Formal semantics and expressiveness”. In: *Software & Systems Modeling* 3.1 (2004), pp. 9–30.
- [RJB04] James Rumbaugh, Ivar Jacobson, and Grady Booch. *Unified Modeling Language Reference Manual, The (2nd Edition)*. Pearson Higher Education, 2004. ISBN: 0321245628.
- [BK05] Marko Bajec and Marjan Krisper. “A methodology and tool support for managing business rules in organisations”. In: *Information Systems* 30.6 (2005), pp. 423–443. ISSN: 0306-4379. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.is.2004.05.003>. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0306437904000481>.
- [Hau+06] Matthew Hause et al. “The SysML modelling language”. In: *Fifteenth European Systems Engineering Conference*. Vol. 9. 2006, pp. 1–12.

-
- [KM06] Aqueo Kamada and Manuel Mendes. “A Business Rule Engine Applied to Egovernment Services Integration”. In: vol. 189. Aug. 2006, pp. 157–171. ISBN: 0-387-28753-1. DOI: 10.1007/0-387-29773-1_11.
- [Sch06] Douglas C Schmidt. “Model-driven engineering”. In: *Computer-IEEE Computer Society-* 39.2 (2006), p. 25.
- [Coo+07] Steve Cook et al. *Domain-specific development with visual studio dsl tools*. Pearson Education, 2007.
- [Ste+08] Dave Steinberg et al. *EMF: eclipse modeling framework*. Pearson Education, 2008.
- [Lia+09] Senlin Liang et al. “OpenRuleBench: An analysis of the performance of rule engines”. In: Jan. 2009, pp. 601–610. DOI: 10.1145/1526709.1526790.
- [YW09] Chuan Yue and Haining Wang. “Characterizing Insecure Javascript Practices on the Web”. In: *Proceedings of the 18th International Conference on World Wide Web. WWW '09*. Madrid, Spain: Association for Computing Machinery, 2009, pp. 961–970. ISBN: 9781605584874. DOI: 10.1145/1526709.1526838. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1145/1526709.1526838>.
- [LGX10] Di Liu, Tao Gu, and Jiang-Ping Xue. “Rule Engine based on improvement Rete algorithm”. In: *The 2010 International Conference on Apperceiving Computing and Intelligence Analysis Proceeding*. 2010, pp. 346–349. DOI: 10.1109/ICACIA.2010.5709916.
- [ZFL10] Kunhua Zhu, Junhui Fu, and Yancui Li. “Research the performance testing and performance improvement strategy in web application”. In: *2010 2nd International Conference on Education Technology and Computer*. Vol. 2. 2010, pp. V2-328-V2-332. DOI: 10.1109/ICETC.2010.5529374.
- [Hit+12] Pascal Hitzler et al. “OWL 2 Web Ontology Language Primer (Second Edition)”. In: 2012.
- [FK13] Hans-Georg Fill and Dimitris Karagiannis. “On the conceptualisation of modelling methods using the ADOxx meta modelling platform”. In: *Enterprise Modelling and Information Systems Architectures (EMISAJ)* 8.1 (2013), pp. 4–25.
- [Syr+13] Eugene Syriani et al. “AToMPM: A web-based modeling environment”. In: *Joint proceedings of MODELS'13 Invited Talks, Demonstration Session, Poster Session, and ACM Student Research Competition co-located with the 16th International Conference on Model Driven Engineering Languages and Systems (MODELS 2013): September 29-October 4, 2013, Miami, USA*. 2013, pp. 21–25.
- [Mar+14] Miklós Maróti et al. “Next generation (meta) modeling: web-and cloud-based collaborative tool infrastructure.” In: *MPM@ MoDELS 1237* (2014), pp. 41–60.

- [Woe+14] William Van Woensel et al. “A Comparison of Mobile Rule Engines for Reasoning on Semantic Web Based Health Data”. In: *2014 IEEE/WIC/ACM International Joint Conferences on Web Intelligence (WI) and Intelligent Agent Technologies (IAT)*. Vol. 1. 2014, pp. 126–133. DOI: 10.1109/WI-IAT.2014.25.
- [Man+15] Rami Mansouri et al. “Modelling and testing the performance of a commercial ammonia/water absorption chiller using Aspen-Plus platform”. In: *Energy* 93 (2015), pp. 2374–2383.
- [FL16] Amjad Fayoumi and Pericles Loucopoulos. “Conceptual modeling for the design of intelligent and emergent information systems”. In: *Expert Systems with Applications* 59 (2016), pp. 174–194.
- [Obj16] Object Management Group (OMG). *Meta-Object Facility (MOF) Specification, Version 2.5.1*. OMG Document Number formal/2006-01-01 (<https://www.omg.org/spec/MOF/>). 2016.
- [Pet17] Dušan Petković. “JSON integration in relational database systems”. In: *Int J Comput Appl* 168.5 (2017), pp. 14–19.
- [Kön18] Stephan Königer. *OCL.js*. Version 1.2.0. Dec. 2018. URL: <https://github.com/SteKoe/ocl.js>.
- [San+18] Kurt Sandkuhl et al. “From expert discipline to common practice: a vision and research agenda for extending the reach of enterprise modeling”. In: *Business & Information Systems Engineering* 60.1 (2018), pp. 69–80.
- [SS18] E.V. Sunitha and Philip Samuel. “Object constraint language for code generation from activity models”. In: *Information and Software Technology* 103 (2018), pp. 92–111. ISSN: 0950-5849. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.infsof.2018.06.010>. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0950584916304190>.
- [Ham19] Cache Hamm. *json-rules-engine*. Version 2.3.6. May 2019. URL: <https://github.com/CacheControl/json-rules-engine>.
- [Ver20] Francois Vernadat. “Enterprise modelling: Research review and outlook”. In: *Computers in Industry* 122 (2020), p. 103265.
- [Muf21] Fill Hans-Georg Muff Fabian. “Initial Concepts for Augmented and Virtual Reality-based Enterprise Modeling.” In: *ER Demos/Posters*. 2021, pp. 49–54.
- [Sat21] Mithun Satheesh. *node-rules*. Version 7.1.0. May 2021. URL: <https://github.com/mithunsatheesh/node-rules>.
- [Sta21] StatCounter.com. *Browser Market Share Worldwide*. 2021. URL: <https://gs.statcounter.com/browser-market-share> (visited on 05/29/2021).
- [The21] Frank Thelen. *rools*. Version 2.3.0. May 2021. URL: <https://github.com/frankthelen/rools>.
- [Jon22] Lars Holmberg Jonatan Heyman. *locust.io*. Version 2.8.6. Apr. 2022. URL: <https://github.com/locustio/locust>.
- [max22] sean maxwell. *Trool*. Version 2.0.3. Mar. 2022. URL: <https://github.com/seanpmaxwell/Trool>.

- [Muf22] Fill Hans-Georg Muff Fabian Borcard Daniel. *ThreeJS-Modeling-ToolkitTypeScriptMetamodel*. Version 1.0.0. Aug. 2022. URL: https://diuf-gitlab.unifr.ch/digits/ThreeJS-Modeling-Toolkit_TypeScript_Metamodel.
- [Grone] The Business Rules Group. *Defining Business Rules What Are They Really?* Tech. rep. Business Rules Group, 2000 [Online]. URL: https://www.businessrulesgroup.org/first_paper/BRG-whatIsBR_3ed.pdf.

A Performance Test Report

Locust Test Report

During: 11/05/2022, 10:50:37 - 11/05/2022, 10:57:55

Target Host: http://localhost:8000

Script: locustfile.py

Request Statistics

Method	Name	# Requests	# Fails	Average (ms)	Min (ms)	Max (ms)	Average size (bytes)	RPS	Failures/s
GET	/instances/objectInstance_rules_test/91a89eeb-3874-4225-867e-993943c1da38/?engine=jsonRulesEngine	13906	449	1035	3	3795	104	31.8	1.0
GET	/instances/objectInstance_rules_test/91a89eeb-3874-4225-867e-993943c1da38/?engine=ocl	13868	488	1040	3	3938	104	31.7	1.1
GET	/instances/objectInstance_rules_test/91a89eeb-3874-4225-867e-993943c1da38/?engine=roots	13671	473	1047	3	3775	100	31.2	1.1
GET	/instances/objectInstance_rules_test/f0ffdbb4-0d0c-4b38-983b-d927c785c02d/?engine=jsonRulesEngine	13843	489	1088	9	4081	157	31.6	1.1
GET	/instances/objectInstance_rules_test/f0ffdbb4-0d0c-4b38-983b-d927c785c02d/?engine=ocl	13713	527	1084	7	4185	130	31.3	1.2
GET	/instances/objectInstance_rules_test/f0ffdbb4-0d0c-4b38-983b-d927c785c02d/?engine=roots	13801	493	1082	7	4191	137	31.5	1.1
Aggregated		82802	2919	1062	3	4191	122	189.2	6.7

Response Time Statistics

Method	Name	50%ile (ms)	60%ile (ms)	70%ile (ms)	80%ile (ms)	90%ile (ms)	95%ile (ms)	99%ile (ms)	100%ile (ms)
GET	/instances/objectInstance_rules_test/91a89eeb-3874-4225-867e-993943c1da38/?engine=jsonRulesEngine	1100	1300	1600	1700	1900	2000	2800	3800
GET	/instances/objectInstance_rules_test/91a89eeb-3874-4225-867e-993943c1da38/?engine=ocl	1200	1300	1600	1700	1900	2000	2800	3900
GET	/instances/objectInstance_rules_test/91a89eeb-3874-4225-867e-993943c1da38/?engine=roots	1200	1400	1600	1700	1900	2000	2800	3800
GET	/instances/objectInstance_rules_test/f0ffdbb4-0d0c-4b38-983b-d927c785c02d/?engine=jsonRulesEngine	1200	1400	1600	1700	1900	2100	2800	4100
GET	/instances/objectInstance_rules_test/f0ffdbb4-0d0c-4b38-983b-d927c785c02d/?engine=ocl	1200	1400	1600	1700	1900	2100	2900	4200
GET	/instances/objectInstance_rules_test/f0ffdbb4-0d0c-4b38-983b-d927c785c02d/?engine=roots	1200	1400	1600	1700	1900	2100	2900	4200
Aggregated		1200	1400	1600	1700	1900	2100	2800	4200

Failures Statistics

Method	Name	Error	Occurrences
GET	/instances/objectInstance_rules_test/f0ffdbb4-0d0c-4b38-983b-d927c785c02d/?engine=jsonRulesEngine	500 Server Error: Internal Server Error for url: http://localhost:8000/instances/objectInstance_rules_test/f0ffdbb4-0d0c-4b38-983b-d927c785c02d/?engine=jsonRulesEngine	489
GET	/instances/objectInstance_rules_test/f0ffdbb4-0d0c-4b38-983b-d927c785c02d/?engine=ocl	500 Server Error: Internal Server Error for url: http://localhost:8000/instances/objectInstance_rules_test/f0ffdbb4-0d0c-4b38-983b-d927c785c02d/?engine=ocl	527
GET	/instances/objectInstance_rules_test/91a89eeb-3874-4225-867e-993943c1da38/?engine=ocl	500 Server Error: Internal Server Error for url: http://localhost:8000/instances/objectInstance_rules_test/91a89eeb-3874-4225-867e-993943c1da38/?engine=ocl	488
GET	/instances/objectInstance_rules_test/91a89eeb-3874-4225-867e-993943c1da38/?engine=jsonRulesEngine	500 Server Error: Internal Server Error for url: http://localhost:8000/instances/objectInstance_rules_test/91a89eeb-3874-4225-867e-993943c1da38/?engine=jsonRulesEngine	449
GET	/instances/objectInstance_rules_test/f0ffdbb4-0d0c-4b38-983b-d927c785c02d/?engine=rools	500 Server Error: Internal Server Error for url: http://localhost:8000/instances/objectInstance_rules_test/f0ffdbb4-0d0c-4b38-983b-d927c785c02d/?engine=rools	493
GET	/instances/objectInstance_rules_test/91a89eeb-3874-4225-867e-993943c1da38/?engine=rools	500 Server Error: Internal Server Error for url: http://localhost:8000/instances/objectInstance_rules_test/91a89eeb-3874-4225-867e-993943c1da38/?engine=rools	473

Charts

Final ratio

Ratio per User class

- 33.3% ocl_client
 - 50.0% test_blocking_rule
 - 50.0% test_accepting_rule
- 33.5% jsonRuleEngine_client
 - 50.0% test_blocking_rule
 - 50.0% test_accepting_rule
- 33.3% roots_client
 - 50.0% test_blocking_rule
 - 50.0% test_accepting_rule

Total ratio

- 33.3% ocl_client
 - 16.6% test_blocking_rule
 - 16.6% test_accepting_rule
- 33.5% jsonRuleEngine_client
 - 16.8% test_blocking_rule
 - 16.8% test_accepting_rule
- 33.3% roots_client
 - 16.6% test_blocking_rule
 - 16.6% test_accepting_rule

B Important Snippet Of Code

B.1 Integration Of OCL.js

```
1  /**
2   * Create an empty engine
3   */
4  const oclEngine = OclEngine.create();
5
6  /**
7   * Link inner type to custom OCL types
8   * # to be referenced by the user
9   * Then register them in the engine
10  */
11  const customTypes = {
12    "SceneType": SceneType,
13    "SceneInstance": SceneInstance,
14    "ClassInstance": ClassInstance
15  }
16  oclEngine.registerTypes(customTypes);
17
18  /**
19   * Add the rules to the engine
20   */
21  for (const rule of constraints){
22    oclEngine.addOclExpression(rule.value);
23  }
24
25  /**
26   * Test the rules against the object
27   */
28  const result_test_rules =
29  ↪ oclEngine.evaluate(objectToTest);
30
31  return {
32    state: result_test_rules.getResult(),
33    failed: result_test_rules.getNamesOfFailedInvs(),
34    passed: null
35  }
```

B.2 Integration Of JSON-rule-engine

```
1  /**
2   * Create an empty rule engine
3   */
4  const engine = new Engine()
5
```

```

6  /**
7   * Add the count operators to the engine
8   * The count operators counts the length of an array
9   * and compare it to a parameter
10  */
11 engine.addOperator('countLessThan', (factValue,
12   ↪  jsonValue) => {
13     return factValue.length < jsonValue
14   })
15 engine.addOperator('countGreaterThanInclusive',
16   ↪  (factValue, jsonValue) => {
17     return factValue.length >= jsonValue
18   })
19 /**
20  * Add the rules to the engine
21  */
22 for (const rule of constraints){
23   engine.addRule(JSON.parse(rule.value))
24 }
25 /**
26  * for testing purposes only
27  */
28 engine.addFact('booltrue', true)
29
30 /**
31  * run the engine against the current object
32  */
33 const msgs = await (engine.run(objectToTest))
34
35 /**
36  * Get the property message of the failed events and push
37  ↪  it to the array
38  */
39 const failedMsgs: string[] = []
40 for (const vnt of msgs.failureEvents){
41   failedMsgs.push(vnt.params.message)
42 }
43 return { state: false, failed: failedMsgs, passed:null };

```

B.3 Integration Of Rools

```

1  /**
2   * create an empty engine
3   */
4  const rools = new Rools();
5

```

```

6  /**
7   * create a js object to catch de result of the rules
8   */
9  const facts = {
10     result: [],
11     object: objectToTest
12 };
13
14 /**
15  * set of rule to be applied
16  */
17 const rule_obvTrue = new Rule({
18     name: 'obviously true rule',
19     when: (facts) => true,
20     then: (facts) => {facts.result.push('Always true
    ↪ rule')},
21 });
22
23 const rule_obvFalse = new Rule({
24     name: 'obviously false rule',
25     when: (facts) => false,
26     then: (facts) => {facts.result.push('Always false
    ↪ rule')},
27 });
28
29 const rule_OnlyOneStart = new Rule({
30     name: 'Only one start class',
31     when: (facts) => {
32         let seen=0;
33         for (const current_class of
    ↪ facts.object.class_instances){
34             if (current_class.uuid_class ===
    ↪ "d40002db-1d52-473f-a104-3b131c38ee7e"){
35                 seen +=1
36             }
37         }
38         return seen >=2;},
39     then: (facts) => {facts.result.push('More than one
    ↪ start event')},
40 });
41
42 const rule_MoreThanOneStart = new Rule({
43     name: 'Only one start class',
44     when: (facts) => {
45         let seen=0;
46         for (const current_class of
    ↪ facts.object.class_instances){
47             if (current_class.uuid_class ===
    ↪ "d40002db-1d52-473f-a104-3b131c38ee7e"){
48                 seen +=1

```

```
49         }
50     }
51     return seen <2;},
52     then: (facts) => {facts.result.push('Only one start
53     ↪ event')},
54 });
55 /**
56  * register the rules to the engine
57  */
58 const rules: Rule[] = []
59 rules.push(rule_obvFalse, rule_obvTrue, rule_OnlyOneStart,
60 ↪ rule_MoreThanOneStart)
61 await rools.register(rules);
62 /**
63  * evaluate the rules against the object to test
64  */
65 const {accessedByPremises, accessedByActions, fired } =
66 ↪ await rools.evaluate(facts);
67 if(fired >0){
68     return {state: false, failed: facts.result,
69     ↪ passed:accessedByPremises.filter(n =>
70     ↪ !accessedByActions.includes(n))};
71 }else {
72     return {state: true, failed: facts.result,
73     ↪ passed:accessedByPremises.filter(n =>
74     ↪ !accessedByActions.includes(n))};
75 }
```

Declaration Of Authorship

I confirm with my signature that I have personally written the thesis using only the sources and aids listed and that I have marked verbatim quotations and paraphrases as such. I am aware that otherwise the faculty has the right, according to the decision of the faculty council of 09.11.2004, to revoke the to withdraw the title awarded on the basis of this work. I hereby further declare that this thesis or parts thereof have not yet been submitted in this form elsewhere as an examination performance, in accordance with the decision of the Faculty Council of 18.11.2013.

Fribourg, the

Daniel Borcard